

SUBJECTIVE PREJUDICE AS A BARRIER TO THE TEACHING OF CULTURES CHARACTERISTICALLY OF AFRICAN ORIGIN

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7916646

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ABSTRACT

This work addresses a theme that aims to analyze the subjective preconception how it enters into the teaching of cultures, of African origin characteristics. It is a bibliographic, factual, analytical investigation, which seeks to synthesize the values of a culture based on Eurocentrism and which, as a rule, seeks to deny a whole culture that does not fit into this idealized profile. Its general objective is to analyze the weight of cultural education that forms a type of citizen full of preconceptions, without being able to realize that it is, and a teacher who does so, without the awareness that he does so, because it denies students access to such topics, denying them a broader study on the cultural aspect and the influence on the formation of the specific Brazilian culture. This research chose dialectical materialism as its directional research method, considering that it is the best way to analyze, discuss and thus understand the internal and external causes of the object. The conclusions reached are that there is a need for deeper training of teachers in human areas, especially graduates in Pedagogy, because these professionals occupy 50% of the entire academic life of the students of the Basic education.

Keywords: African matrix culture. Pedagogical praxis. Subjective preconception.

INTRODUCTION

The teaching praxis can never be understood as an act isolated from the whole environment that involves the actors and their action results in the possibility of interpreting the phenomenon of learning and, in particular, the formation of the student's personological structure. In this mechanism, the one who teaches and the one who learns stands out, both active individuals, marked by the subjectivity that built them and by the expectation of training; therefore, none of this can be ignored, because in doing so, both those involved in the didactic process end up enslaved by a situation of external control that urges them to follow a line of subjective reasoning, contradicting their way of expressing and understanding things which are necessary effective and efficient actions of reasoning and reflection, since they are phylogenetic and cultural phenomena, and may fall into the serious risk of interpreting certain attitudes as something consensual and, in the sequence, making it commonplace. This is the problem that has been happening with the didactic processes regarding the teaching and learning of African-based content.

The teaching of contents of African matrices encounter several obstacles in regular schools, especially due to the fact that an entire white, European, Protestant, Judeo-Christian culture permeated the formation of the Brazilian State since the arrival of the colonizers, in the 16th century, and the way What they found to stop a culture as strong as the African one was the demonization of it and its epistemological and epistemological contents. In the wake of this, Jesuit-oriented education took care of overvaluing European culture and its principles, to the detriment of belittling the culture of those who were in a state of subjugation, despite demonstrating a high level of spirituality and technical knowledge. The priests created a whole pejorative value judgment about African customs, traditions and principles that made them an object of horror.²⁵

This type of didactic action meant that, from an early age, children grew up learning to avoid these situations of approaching traditional elements of African cultures for fear of divine punishment. This subjective interpretation, in relation to the theme, gives rise to what we call *subjective prejudice*, which can be translated as fear of something that is not known; at most, one has a [de]formed view on the subject and this is carried throughout life and, even after graduating, having reached a certain degree of intellectual enlightenment, the feeling of fear persists, like an amalgam [*unresolved*], which means that in the application of their

²⁵The word *horror* is understood, according to its semantic meaning, as *aversion* (Authors' Note, 2023).

pedagogical praxis, the education professional is not able to think, much less act in an interdisciplinary way and when he addresses the topic about cultures of African matrices, he does so superficially and prejudice appears in its own difficulty of ideological expression.

This is a problem that has been permeating Brazilian education, which, despite having created a law that obliges school curricula to include themes of an Afro hue, a fact that, by itself, already demonstrates the disregard for all the historical-cultural and phylogenetic formation of the nation, because the Africans who landed here brought with them a whole range of values and technical-methodological instruments that would earn greatness of an epistemological and epistemological nature to a people that would still be formed, given that a single native group lived here, called Indians by the colonizers, because of erroneous geographical interpretation committed by navigators.

Africans, in their homeland, already constituted themselves as a solid nation and had a consolidated culture in various fields of human knowledge, ranging from writing, literature, medicine, agriculture, astronomy, mining engineering, religion, mineral extraction and other aspects that, because of the regime to which they were submitted when they arrived in Brazil, they were prevented from exercising, as a form of absolute domination.

However, the *establishment* knew well that prohibition for the sake of prohibition would not be enough, because this was too abstract to have practical effect; it was necessary to create a mechanism that, once applied to objective reality and on the target object, would itself feed the repressive machine, becoming more powerful with each attempt to overcome it by those who were under its direct yoke. It is there that they elaborate the process of subjective prejudice, a machination that the Catholic Church approved and that, with its institutional Christianity, took care of fomenting terror in the terrified minds of a people that was beginning to be formed.

As a result, an entire mystical construction of denial of African precepts was insurgently implanted in the spirit and culture of Brazilians, via religion, via Jesuit education, via tales that, for a people imprisoned in the midst of a wild land covered with forest, as the Brazilian lands were, all that seemed very real. Even when education expands, this after more than 300 years of European colonization, the condition for building the feeling of superiority of white attributes over those originally attributed to Africans and, consequently, to their descendants (Afro-Brazilians) it continued as a tradition rooted in the psychological mechanisms of didactic-pedagogical action, always expressed in a subjective way.

SUBJECTIVE PREJUDICE REGARDING AFRO-DESCENDENTS AND THEIR CULTURAL EXPRESSION

The main problem faced is one whose real dimension is not known, because it sub-exists, masked under various subtle forms of confrontation that are not openly presented to those who suffer its impacts. With the Afro-Brazilian culture, this has been happening since the Africans arrived here, brought to this continent as slaves, because it happened that, when they arrived on the African continent, the future colonizers [among them, Portuguese explorers] were faced *with* a civilization already consummated in all its cultural aspects, including a well-organized political system of government.

This represented a hard blow, because they expected to find a people with a retrograde economy, with an archaic system of political governance and without an educational structure, something that proved to be contrary to the thought that Europeans had of peoples who did not belong to the continent.

This condition already makes it clear that there was an established preconception about the inhabitants of African regions still unexplored by the white culture and here, the need arises to explain the semantic sense of preconception, in which this is a concept formed *a priori*, that is, before one has the minimum of systematic knowledge about the object that one intends to approach and in the eagerness of vanity, a vision of inferiority is created that begins to grow throughout the continent, aided by the Catholic Church who sought new domains to expand his teachings of the Christian faith.

In the *Notebook for the fight against discrimination*, produced by the São Paulo State Department of Education, the following definition of prejudice is found: “opinion formed without knowledge of the facts; judgment made without reflection; old and routine idea that is not supported by serious evidence and arguments; early concept; superstition” (SÃO PAULO, 1987, p. 10).

This conceptual approach presented above is based on the interpretation of the word formed from a radical and a word, suggesting that it refers to an *opinion* issued, in a hurried way, in relation to an object about which one has little or no knowledge. . In the case of *subjective prejudice*, this has an even more catastrophic effect, because the one that expels it against a certain group, in the case posed in this work against an entire culture and not necessarily against a people, given that the Afro-descendants who are, in Brazil, they are Brazilian citizens and this cannot be ignored by any of the parties, under penalty of losing an

identity conquered for centuries and which is consolidated in the countless constitutions that form the jurisdictional scope of the Brazilian Nation.

When the Society of Jesus was present in Brazilian lands, the first care they took was to place any and all religions other than Roman Christianity under suspicion and they implanted terror over the natives and when the Africans arrived here, brought in entourages that had been carrying a whole high cultural baggage, there was no other way out than to create stereotypes in every way about them and their cultural-phylogenetic processes, distorting and negating everything that was related to them, directly and indirectly.

It was not difficult to find supporters for the unfounded theories of the Society of Jesus professors about Africans, because the latter were in a condition of extreme servitude, isolated from their manes and their motherland. And when a people is prevented from expressing their faith in their manes and in their domestic gods, the first step is taken to make them submissive, because they will never resort to the God of a stranger to themselves and their ancestors and, without the protection of faith, no human being resists [*for a long time*] and, as an end to this torture imposed by the aggressor, ends up giving in to his whims.

Enslavement is not *only* intended to submit the other to its dominion and exploit its workforce, because in order to persist, it needs to subvert the spirit of the individual subjugated to the double belief that their culture and everything it represents is inferior to that of that one. who holds power over himself and still have to lead the individual or the subjugated people to believe that the dominator's culture and everything it represents is superior. For this reason, mechanisms for appropriating the subjective domain should be created beyond the domain of the body and the workforce.

The intention, not explicit, is to maintain a system that provides a condition of inferiority *ad infinitum* and even if mechanisms are created and applied to face the problem, the elements not perceived by reason, prevent the achievement of efficient and effective results, even in the space of school activity, no matter how much one wants to claim its superiority and neutrality in relation to social events, this simple-minded, naive and devoid of logic thinking is the great achievement of the thinking of the operative and dominant status *quo* . The school and all its entourage of repeaters of ideologies do nothing more than reaffirm the prevailing social thought, even when it believes it is fighting against it.

In this sense, Martins will state that,

Today's society often makes reflections, criticisms and questions about itself difficult. Such facts not only produce the alienation of human beings, but also propitious conditions for the appearance of prejudice. A society based on

prejudice is a society without reflection and without reason (MARTINS, 1988, p. 17).

In the field of Education, the teacher who claims in his defense that he never speaks against the culture of others, especially against the African mans, is wrong, because it is enough that he omits to offer space for his students to know and discuss the beliefs and values historical backgrounds of their ancestors who once took care of maintaining the *status quo* of prejudice against each other. And his passionate defense that he has no prejudices against anything, against any type or against anyone already demonstrates that he does not know himself and that, it is precisely for this reason that he becomes subject to the obsessive manipulation of the dominant groups.

Only self-knowledge and the systematic study of foreign cultures are capable of providing conditions for those involved not to be captured in discourses where statistical probability and the expropriation of the right to defense are spoken louder. Martins (1998) argues that,

Prejudice is constituted in the meditations of subjectivity and social relations and, therefore, both the study of this theme and its transformation are extensive, complex and involve a variety of factors that must be analyzed, even in the most subjective and specific manifestations of prejudice. Thus, prejudice is a product and producer of intermediations between subjectivity and society (MARTINS, 1988, p. 17).

The terrain of subjectivity is a field that extends beyond and beyond the individual, making it impossible to interpret it in a hasty way and, when in the classroom, in which the most restrained teacher is caught letting out a sigh of dismay when a black student asks him a question, apparently simple and that, for this teacher, anyone should know, it is clear that there is, rooted in his unconscious, a form of veiled prejudice against a certain group of students.

MECHANISMS FOR FIGHTING SUBJECTIVE PREJUDICE IN RELATION TO AFRO-BRAZILIAN CULTURE

The main way to combat *preconceptions* is through systematic, deep and categorized studies in the search for a solid understanding of things that are and things that are not, trying to understand and understand why at times they are discussed and at times others are not. There is no way to extinguish or, at least, minimize the impacts caused by a tradition of exclusion of knowledge just by denying that such and such a thing exists, because it cannot be seen and it is

through this bias that the prejudiced continues to remain as such, because, in the first instance, he refuses to reflect on his everyday attitudes.

There is no feeling or knowledge, however subjective it may be transmitted or acquired through *osmotic categorization* . Everything in the human being must be taught; therefore, prejudice against certain groups and here, we deal with Afro-descendant groups and their entire culture [*in all biases*], this also obeys historical construction standards, in which a whole pedagogy of exclusion was thought and applied on the subject, always with the bias of the supremacy of *white values over the values of Africans and their descendants in Tierras Brasilis*. The values of a nation or culture are destroyed and everything that follows is nothing more than a consequence, there is no one to blame for the problem raised and everything that comes in the wake is treated as being normal; as if the moral deterioration of a people, a nation, a culture, was the most natural thing to do or let happen. And, when questioning such attitudes, there will be those who say that it is up to the oppressed to rise up and defend themselves against the injuries they suffer.

It so happens that, in a very short time, even the victim adheres to the aggression, because he starts to interpret it as a form of power and the truth that attacks him starts to be seen as a truth that strengthens, even if it is in a way negative and that is where all the risk is imposed on a culture that starts to take prejudice as something natural to its existence, a mark of its culture and that there is no way to fight against it. This form of adherence to the oppressive power, which we allude to, can even be that of silence, the passive acceptance of an existential condition, the result of a whole engineering set up and developed by those who [supposedly] won the *war* . However, it is necessary to analyze with the deepest care, the situation that, the need to use such an arsenal to suppress the expression of a culture is already a clear sign that it is very powerful and frightening, only for its strength and splendor.

This problem is followed by the fact that newspapers have performed an immense negative service in the fight against all forms of prejudice, especially against cultures of Afro-Brazilian origin and orientation, because their reports must be marked by exacerbated sensationalism, affected, in that a whole dramatization is built, in which all the action is exposed in a clear way, dispensing with any and all discourse analysis, content analysis and a situational interpretation.

This type of subjective prejudice in relation to the culture of African origin, assumes itself as an institutionalized prejudice and without realizing it and, for this reason, without understanding or understanding the reasons, The contents involving African and Afro-Brazilian

history and culture, will be removed from the curriculum until that portion remains that the law obliges to support and that ends up relegated to a miserable week, within the school year and in its place an entire opposition culture is offered as an object of value to the student and in the teachers' rooms, It is very common to see professionals say that they teach *that* to students because there is the force of law to oblige, because otherwise, those blasphemies would not be presented to them. It is important to point out that in order to advance in the process of implementing Law 10.639/2003, which makes the teaching of African and Afro-Brazilian history and culture mandatory, continuing training of teachers is necessary, so as not to restrict such an important, urgent and needed in November.

Another ridiculous situation occurs when the teacher, in order to say he is free from prejudice, is decked out in Afro-Brazilian clothing to celebrate *Black Consciousness Day* and the school is filled with posters with cut-out phrases about humanism, awareness and the fight against all forms of prejudice against Afro-Brazilian beliefs, religions and culture. None of this could prove to be more characteristic of the situation of ignorance on the subject in question. It is enough to ask when the professor of literature recommended a book by an author of African and/or Afro-Brazilian origin so that his students could read it and prepare reviews, organize study groups or syntheses. And the Arts teacher, when he goes to exhibit paintings from the Brazilian slavery period, makes a point of showing the African or Afro-descendant in tattered clothes and the boss in slender, elegant clothes and the women, in the same way, in which the employers are shown in the images of the pictures and textbooks with their long blonde wigs imported from England and the black women, always demoted performing heavy tasks, devoid of any adornment that enchants them.

There is no need to stereotype Afro-descendants through vituperation, nor to say that he is prejudiced, because his didactic choices already say exactly what he thinks about the subject and how he reflects on the educational reality. This type of prejudice is a cancer in society that metastasizes from the process of formal educational training, when it refuses to think about the forms of exposure to which each culture is presented to students.

In history classes, when dealing with the battles in which Brazil participated, it is omitted that Afro-descendants were at the forefront and that it was thanks to their commitment to war that the nation emerged victorious. On the contrary, he does not deny his participation, but in the same way, the subject is not touched upon, therefore, the idea that is formed is that the African and his descendants, born here, were only used for manual labor and exploration in the cane fields, cocoa trees and other modalities.

In Geography, it is not explained, perhaps even due to the teacher's initial training process, which had no contact with the discussions focused on the theme in question, that it was thanks to the Africans that it became possible to explore gold in the lands of the Captaincy of Minas Gerais, because they had knowledge of mine excavation and knew how to distinguish fool's gold ²⁶from real gold and also fool's diamond from real diamond.

In Portuguese Language classes, it is only about the origin of the language as being of European origin and, there is no discussion of how much Africans influenced the formation of the Brazilian Portuguese that is spoken today. A semantic of words that were introduced by a Eurocentric bias is studied and the student is denied contact with the African lexicon.

In this, what we have is a denial of the broad right to knowledge of Brazilian culture that, far beyond being treated as a *miscegenation* of three cultures, which already brings in itself, a petty speech that aims to hide this potential for semantic exploration -cultural, because something can only be made known, in its maximum depth and expansion, if it is isolated and analyzed from its particular and singular aspects. Science does not work with a set of things, with miscegenations; scientific study is concerned with reducing the object to its atomic particle. Brazilian culture is a solid culture; but that, to be understood as such, the student must know in depth the epistemological and epistemological bases that sustain it as such and, in the same proportion, know the cultures of the peoples that came here, in all their particularities and singularities. Resistance to such an intervention has nothing to do with prejudice, subjective or otherwise; it has to do with ignorance itself, the product of poor school and academic education.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Subjective prejudice in relation to African and/or Afro-Brazilian culture is a structural problem that prevents an efficient pedagogical practice in terms of forming a student who understands the meaning of culture as a whole historical burden that makes up his personal background.

With regard to Africa and all its historical composition, the first point to consider is that, in a different way, the knowledge of this continent and all its people, with its culture and distinctions, is the most objective way of approaching an understanding of the personological structure of the Brazilian people.

²⁶ Popular name given to iron pyrite due to its metallic luster and golden-yellow color, similar to gold (Authors' Note, 2023).

Deprived of part of the culture that aggregates important and essential elements for the formation of the personological structure of Brazilian citizens and it is mentioned here, the African phylogenetic heritage, with all its values, beliefs and knowledge, what you have is an individual who will tend to express prejudiced attitudes because of lack of knowledge and not necessarily because of a legitimate conviction.

Teachers, ignorant of these maneuvers elaborated by the school, via the official curriculum and especially via the hidden curriculum, end up believing that they are following superior orders, when, in fact, they themselves feel free to deny their students this broader access to the culture of their historical ancestors. It could not be otherwise, because the dominant social system is perverse and creates a strategy so that, throughout their student career, they only know what interests the establishment *and* not what they would have an effective need to know in order to form a critical conscience. about the whole.

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